

NMR Spectra of Unsymmetrical Meta Disubstituted Benzenes Oriented in the Nematic Phase. The Spectrum of *m*-Chlorobromobenzene

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The NMR spectrum of *m*-chlorobromobenzene has been investigated in the nematic phase of 4-methoxy benzylidene-4-amino- α -methyl cinnamic acid *n*-propylester at room temperature.

The spectrum does not permit the determination of all the direct couplings and the chemical shifts uniquely. The reasons are discussed. If, however, it is assumed that the structure of the proton skeleton of the molecule does not deviate significantly from that of *m*-dichloro or *m*-dibromobenzene, the spectrum can be analysed and it is possible to derive the geometry information. The results are presented.

Orientation of the molecule has been found to be similar to that in *m*-dichloro and *m*-dibromobenzene.

The NMR spectra of symmetrical *m*-disubstituted benzenes and pyrimidine which belong to the type AB₂C have been reported earlier¹⁻³. The spectra of the unsymmetrical *m*-disubstituted benzenes which geometrically do not deviate significantly from the symmetrical cases but require three parameters to specify the molecular orientation do not seem to have been reported in the literature. The present investigation was undertaken to find out whether the spectra of the two classes differ from each other appreciably or not and to find out how much structural information can be derived in the unsymmetrical cases. The results on *m*-chlorobromobenzene are reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

A 13 mole per cent solution of commercially available *m*-chlorobromobenzene was studied in the nematic phase of 4-methoxy benzylidene-4-amino- α -methyl cinnamic acid-*n*-propyl ester (I) at room temperature with the help of a Varian HR spectrometer operating at 56.4 MHz. Several spectra were recorded and the statistical error in the measurement of line positions was found to be 2 Hz. Average line width was 13 Hz.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the spectrum : The spectrum of the compound is shown in the figure. It is quite similar to that of the symmetrical compound¹.

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Analysis of the spectrum was carried out with the help of LAOCOONOR⁴ programme on a CDC-3600 computer.

Fig. 1 Observed (A) and Calculated (B) spectra of *m*-chlorobromobenzene oriented in the nematic phase of (I). Concentration = 13 mole%, temperature = 28°, spectrometer frequency = 56.4 MHz.

It was found that if the analysis is carried out as a general ABCD case, it is not possible to derive the values of the direct couplings D_{12} , D_{14} , D_{23} , D_{34} and the chemical shifts ν_2 and ν_4 individually. The reason for such an indeterminacy lies in the fact that the proton skeleton of the molecule has near perfect C_{2v} -symmetry. The spectral lines arising due to the asymmetry caused by the substituents are not detectable under the present conditions. However, it is approximately an AA'BB' system since the nuclei 1 and 3 and 2 and 4 do not have appreciable chemical shift between themselves. The degeneracy conditions for AA'BB' system discussed in an earlier communication⁵ are fulfilled here and hence the spectrum is not sensitive to the determination of all the parameters. Therefore, under the present conditions of orientation, the possibility of a study which permits the determination of the differences in geometry in various unsymmetrical *m*-di-substituted benzenes arising due to the substituents, is ruled out. However, it can be derived with the help of the LAOCOONOR programme that the sums $D_{12}+D_{14}$, $D_{23}+D_{34}$ and $\nu_2+\nu_4$ can be evaluated individually with reasonable precision. Thus if it is assumed that the proton skeleton of *m*-chlorobromobenzene does not deviate significantly from C_{2v} -symmetry i.e., $D_{12} = D_{14}$, $D_{23} = D_{34}$ and $\nu_2 = \nu_4$, all the parameters can be determined and the values are reproduced in the table. The r.m.s. error between the observed and the calculated line positions was 1.9 Hz. Errors of the various parameters were derived in a manner similar to the one described in reference⁶. Values of the indirect couplings used were taken from the literature⁷.

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TABLE

Values of the parameters for m-chlorobromobenzene derived under the assumption of C_{2v} -symmetry for the proton skeleton

Parameter	Value
D_{12}, D_{14}	-49.4 ± 0.2 Hz
D_{23}, D_{34}	-716.4 ± 0.3 Hz
D_{13}	-1.5 ± 0.2 Hz
D_{24}	-182.1 ± 0.5 Hz
$\nu_1 - \nu_2, \nu_1 - \nu_4$	20.5 ± 0.8 Hz
$\nu_3 - \nu_2, \nu_3 - \nu_4$	19.4 ± 0.2 Hz
r_{24}/r_{23}	1.7339 ± 0.0013
S_{11}	0.1203 ± 0.0003
S_{22}	0.0015
S_{33}	-0.1218

Geometry Information : Under the assumption of C_{2v} -symmetry of the proton skeleton, the ratio (r_{24}/r_{23}) can be determined with the help of equations reported earlier³. The value is included in the table. It is interesting to note that it lies in between the value for *m*-dichloro and *m*-dibromobenzenes. The ratios r_{13}/r_{23} and r_{12}/r_{23} ($= 1.99$ and 1.73 respectively) could not be determined to a reasonable precision because of the low degree of orientation of the axis joining the protons 1 and 3. A similar situation was encountered in the symmetrical compounds¹.

Molecular Orientation : Even though it is not possible to determine all the direct couplings in *m*-chlorobromobenzene, it is possible to derive the three orientation parameters to a reasonable precision from D_{24} , ($D_{12} + D_{14}$) and ($D_{23} + D_{34}$) provided that the molecular geometry is accurately known. In absence of the accurate knowledge of the molecular geometry, an assumption of the structure of the symmetrical compound leaves only S_{11} and S_{22} as the independent parameters, S_{12} being zero under these conditions. Values of S_{11} and S_{22} reported in the table have been determined from D_{24} and D_{23} with $r_{24} = 4.297\text{\AA}$. The error of S_{22} is relatively large because of its small magnitude.

The magnitude and the sign of various dipolar couplings indicate that the orientation of the molecule is similar to that of the symmetrical compounds¹.

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